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Informal Land Use in Peripheral Barrios of Quito: Planning Problem, Development Obstacle or Poverty Alleviation?

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Paper prepared for the N-AERUS Workshop, Leuven, May 2001 on "Coping with Informality and Illegality in Human Settlements in Developing Cities".

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Introduction

Informal use of land in many peripheral settlements of Latin American cities is characterised by illegality, by the simultaneous use of land for living and for producing, and by the spatial concentration of kin-related households. Informal land use has been viewed from different perspectives. The *modernisation* perspective, which has influenced many planners in Latin American cities, has held that residential areas should be separate from areas of production. The mixed use of land in the barrios is considered backward and in conflict with modern planning standards. Modernism views such practices as a straightforward problem that needs to be corrected by means of an Urban Master Plan. The *neoliberal* perspective has concentrated principally on the legal aspects of informality. Using neoliberal economic concepts it has been argued that living in an illegal status has negative consequences for the inhabitants of informal settlements. Since they rarely have formal title to the land they inhabit, the residents lack the collateral to raise cash. In neoliberal terms, extralegality is an obstacle to development. Property laws need to be changed to facilitate legalisation thus allowing the poor to realise their development potential. The *grass-roots* perspective has criticised

modernisation-biased planning theory for ignoring the fact that multipurpose land-use is an essential survival strategy of the urban poor in their context of economic insecurity. Indeed, informal use of land is regarded as a means of poverty alleviation. Planning models based on the idea of specialised use of land are deemed irrelevant to the social, economic and cultural needs of low-income populations in informal settlements. To sum up, informal use of land is viewed by the modernisation perspective as a 'planning problem', by the neoliberal perspective as an 'obstacle to development', and by the grassroots perspective as a means of 'poverty alleviation'.

The aim of this paper is to evaluate these three perspectives for the case of the barrios of Quito, Ecuador. The evaluation is based on interviews and first-hand observations on land use evolution in barrio Mena del Hierro carried out over a ten-year period (1990-2000). The methods used for the study are land-use mapping and participatory research. Qualitative interviews were conducted with barrio residents to understand the legal, socio-economic and socio-cultural functions of informal land-use. Selected aspects of the results are given in the text boxes throughout this paper, and further details can be found in Riaño (1999, 2000).

The following three questions are addressed in this paper: (a) what are the characteristics and benefits of informal land-use in the barrios? (b) How does Quito's Master Plan regulate land use in the barrios? (c) What are the socio-economic disadvantages of informality for the poor? The paper is concluded with a discussion of an integrated approach to land-use policies and research in informal settlements.

1. Characteristics and benefits of informal land use

1.1. Illegality

Most residents in the barrios of Quito have formal titles to the land they occupy but they lack permits for how they use their land: (a) areas which are not officially foreseen for housing are urbanised; (b) land is subdivided into lots that are smaller than the minimum permitted by official regulations; (c) buildings are erected in defiance of regulations governing maximum lot occupation and number of floors; (d) businesses operate without complying with land-use regulations. This widespread status of illegality takes on many degrees, but a pattern of evolution is evident. Illegality in individual barrios usually evolves over the years through at least two phases:

Phase 1: The entire settlement is initially illegal, as it has been developed on land which is officially planned for agriculture or ecological reserves.

Phase 2: The use of land for housing becomes authorized and the settlement is legally accepted as part of the city. Land-owners are granted land titles, however, individual constructions, lot subdivisions and businesses within the settlements usually remain without permits from the planning authorities.

In Quito, the speed at which barrios evolve from phase 1 to phase 2 depends to a large extent on political factors. The inhabitants of informal barrios represent a large voting potential. Local parties are willing to grant them favours (e.g. legalisation, infrastructure) in exchange for votes in the elections for city administrators. Thus, despite the illegal beginnings of informal barrios, the majority of them are eventually legalised and officially incorporated in the city. Throughout Latin America this political mechanism, known as *clientelismo*, is a main means by which informal urbanisation becomes legalised.

The evolution of illegal land-use in barrio Mena del Hierro. The history of this informal settlement, located in the northwestern periphery of Quito, illustrates the transition from illegality to legality. The settlement emerged from the illegal subdivision of a cattle-farming *hacienda*. In the early 1970's, cattle farming had lost much of its profitability and the city of Quito had expanded considerably towards the *hacienda*. Given Quito's large demand for low-income accommodation, the most profitable move for the *hacienda* owners was to sell their land for housing. As the change of land use from rural to urban activities was officially not permitted, the *hacienda* owners took advantage of the weaknesses of the legal system to accomplish their purpose. An official permit was obtained in 1972 to subdivide the land into *huertos familiares* (family vegetable gardens), which were to have a minimum lot size of 2500 m² and were to be used exclusively for gardening. In practice, however, the lots were sold for urban housing without having to provide the basic infrastructure or services required for an urban development. In the majority of cases, related migrant families formed groups to buy *huertos familiares* lots collectively, which they subdivided informally between themselves. In other cases, informal land developers bought lots for later illegal subdivision and resale at a considerable profit. Despite its illegal beginning, the *clientelismo* mechanism eventually legalised Mena del Hierro and it became officially part of the municipality of Quito. Practically all the barrios in the Northwest are a result of such illegal subdivisions of *haciendas*, either directly into barrios or indirectly via *huertos familiares*, and in practically all cases, *clientelismo* was the major factor that facilitated the transition from phase one to phase two.

A third phase of evolution can be recognized in many barrios. With time some residents may eventually obtain the permits required to legalise their status, but this is by no means the rule. The present status of the barrios in Quito, for example, is highly heterogeneous with respect to legality. Whether residents finally obtain permits or not depends on a variety of factors. *Clientelismo* politics usually no longer play a role at this stage, because the stakes for the politicians are too low for the work involved. The scattered individuals wanting to obtain permits for single subdivisions, buildings or businesses, do not represent a coherent voting potential and politicians tend to turn their favours to large construction projects elsewhere in the city.

Obtaining building and business permits depends in the first instance on the conscious decisions of individual land-owners. For many residents, the issue of permits arises only well after their buildings or businesses already exist. Often it is an unexpected visit from the planning inspectors that brings the situation to a head. Nevertheless, no land-owners would contemplate modifying or removing one of the existing buildings on their property to comply with the regulations, and the usual solution is to bribe the inspectors. However, business owners and residents wishing to construct new buildings carefully weigh the economic advantages and disadvantages of obtaining official permits. They appreciate, on

the one hand, that a permit opens access to sources of formal credit, and this is in general highly desirable. On the other, they know that obtaining a permit also obliges them to pay taxes and to conform to labour and environmental regulations. This implies higher costs of production, which many small-scale entrepreneurs are unable to afford. Social factors may also influence the will of entrepreneurs to obtain an official permit. For example, parents wanting to bequeath part of their land to their children may feel more motivated to take on the costly paperwork for a permit to allow subdivision or a construction. It is clear that the evolution of illegality is a multifaceted phenomenon that depends on political, economic and social factors.

1.2. Multifunctionality

Even cursory examination of the barrios in Latin America's cities show that residential areas do not merely provide roofs over the heads of low-income populations, but that they are also centres of informal economic production. Barrio settlements usually host agricultural and commercial enterprises, such as vegetable gardens, shops, commercial services and workshops, and small- to medium-sized industries. The nature of such multifunctional land use develops with time. In their initial stage, informal settlements usually have little commercial or industrial activity. In later years, as transport facilities improve and the settlement becomes more integrated into the city, the number of commercial and industrial businesses increases. Depending on the settlements' relative location in the city and the size of available lots, informal settlements can develop into highly dynamic commercial and industrial centres.

Multifunctional land use in Mena del Hierro: 1970-2000. Land is a precious, intensively used resource in the community of Mena del Hierro. Private land plots serve the multiple purposes of housing, production, commerce and recreation. A historical analysis of land use evolution from 1970 to 2000 shows the following patterns. Personal interviews with barrio pioneers reveal that during the 1972-1983 period, housing, agriculture and clay brickworks were the main activities. These three activities were not spatially separated but were pursued concurrently on the same lots where residents lived. Wherever there were houses there were also family crops. Wherever there were brickworks there were also houses and crops. By 1983, brickmaking had lost economic importance and had given way to the construction of new dwellings for rent or for housing kinspeople. Brickmaking was clearly an essential start-up economic activity that allowed certain families to accumulate capital for later investment in housing or taxis. Only two brickmaking industries existed by 1983, and one of these had been transformed to manufacture cement blocks rather than clay bricks. The other change with respect to the years prior to 1983 was the emergence of a secondary-sector industry, metalworking, in the northwestern part of the barrio. Some shops and the primary school had also been constructed. The land-use pattern of mixed housing and crops remained dominant, however. By 1992, two land use trends were recognizable. The primary-sector activities such as agriculture and brickmaking were decreasing in importance or stagnating, while housing, secondary-sector industry, commerce and communal facilities were increasing. The area previously used for crops has been drastically reduced, to the advantage of dwellings, which over the 1983-1992 period doubled in number. Loss of agricultural area has continued steadily through to the year 2000.

Multifunctional land-use serves a valuable social and economic function for the poor. Typically barrio families combine their space for shelter with food-production, business-operation and social activities. Raising animals and crops on the same land as the household dwelling is a convenient means of lowering living costs, food being one of the major expenditures for the poor. Importantly, the use of the household plot for commercial and manufacturing businesses enables the residents to generate employment for themselves, for their family members and for other barrio residents, without incurring the otherwise prohibitive overheads. Finally, the concentration of residential and production activities on the same lot does much to promote social contact and integration among residents.

The value of multifunctional land use for the community of Mena del Hierro.

Multifunctional land use allows barrio residents to use multiple economic strategies to generate income. Residents often combine the renting of buildings for housing or commerce with informal business activity and with occasional or part-time employment in the city. Commercial activities directly benefit the community, as they are aimed at local demand. They include selling items for daily consumption (groceries, bread, medicaments, alcohol, household and school supplies, cooking gas, shoes) as well as providing of important services for the community (clothes-making, repairs of cars, electrical appliances and shoes, hair-dressing, restaurants, billiards, taxi driving, money lending, emigration brokering and rental of sports-grounds). Manufacturing activities are partly aimed at local consumption but mostly at regional and international markets. Brick-, bread- and jewelery makers sell their products in Mena del Hierro, in other informal barrios and to formal businesses in the city. Makers of wooden toys sell their products to the barrio's plush-toy makers as well as to formal industries in the city. Plush-toy makers place their products in regional and international markets. Shoe-making, grocery warehouses, cabinet-making and bodywork fitting is exclusively aimed at urban and regional markets in Quito and petroleum-producing areas in the country.

Urban farming in Mena del Hierro produces valuable corn, potatoes, vegetables and animal foodstuffs. Crop- and animal-raising are traditional practices of the many residents of Mena del Hierro who grew up in rural environments. Corn, an item of utmost importance in the diet of most Ecuadorians, particularly of the popular sectors, is the main crop in the barrio. Animals, especially pigs, rabbits and chickens, are raised in the backyards of lots. Much of the domestic garbage produced by residents has a high organic content and so it is used as compost to fertilise crops.

The concentration of housing units for kin-groups generates common spaces which are very important for social contact, particularly for women. Common services are often located in these spaces, such as water tanks for clothes-washing, and thus women are able to break the isolation of their daily household routines. The social spaces created by the concentration of housing units as well as by the concentration of commercial and manufacturing activities promotes social contact between established barrio residents as well as with populations from the countryside. There is a regular flow of friends and kin, who come from the countryside to live in the barrio for a certain period or permanently, and vice versa. Thus, communication spaces created by multifunctionality are important in maintaining both networks within the barrio and between the barrio and the countryside.

1.3. Kin clusters

A remarkable feature of the social organisation of barrios is the prevalence of kin networks. These networks provide the structural framework for self-help strategies. Trusted family members provide each other with a wide range of support, including money-lending, childcare, assistance in erecting buildings, business labour, transport, employment contacts, moral advice, healthcare and other material and non-material favours. In essence, kin networks are the informal social welfare service of the poor. The efficiency of these networks is increased when the kin members live in the immediate proximity of each other. The related families therefore tend to cluster their dwellings closely on the same or adjoining lots. While each nuclear family tends to have its own house, the network members, particularly women, share much of their daily routines, their appliances and their working space.

The cluster-like residential distribution of kin groups in Mena del Hierro. This is one of the special features of the community of Mena del Hierro. As explained above, many related migrant families formed groups to buy lots collectively in Mena del Hierro and then subdivided the lots among themselves. At the beginning of the 1990s, over 50% of the barrio's households were related to others by immediate kinship, while close or distant family ties related many more. Today, the majority of kin-groups cluster on one or more contiguous land sections, where household members live in separate dwellings but share much of their daily routine, particularly women. Kinship is actually the keystone of community in the barrio. Kin clusters continuously expand, as the second and third generations tend to remain in the barrio when they form a family. The original lots are usually large enough to accommodate the newly-formed families, and many new couples are dependent on the barrio's social and economic networks for childcare and employment possibilities. As a consequence, initial lots have been subdivided many times and will continue to be subdivided.

2. Quito's Urban Master Plan and land use regulations for the barrios

2.1 Commercial and industrial activity in the barrios

Quito's Master Plan regulates the areas where residential, commercial, industrial, public services and ecological activities are permitted (Municipio de Quito, 1992). Compared to modernist segregation models, the plan is much more flexible with respect to land use. The Plan in fact accepts the principle of multifunctionality in residential areas. While multifunctionality is beneficial for the poor, as demonstrated above, unlimited multifunctionality may also have negative consequences. Industrial accidents within residential areas are an obvious example. Clearly, borders need to be drawn. The question is, how should these borders be conceptualised?

Quito's Master Plan uses the concepts of 'environmental impact' and 'compatibility' to delimit the borders. Environmental impact is defined as 'the noise, odours or increased traffic that industrial activities may generate'. Commercial and industrial activities are designated as 'compatible' with

residential areas as long as they 'do not threaten to dominate over the principal use of housing' (Municipio de Quito, 1992:83). Depending on their potential environmental impact, industrial¹ and commercial² activities are classified into groups. Generally, low-impact groups are deemed compatible with residential areas. Middle- and high-impact groups are defined as incompatible and are thus excluded from residential areas.

To what extent is this classification appropriate for the barrios of Quito? In general, the classification of economic activities into groups according to potential impact is good and necessary. However, an evaluation based on the case of barrio Mena del Hierro (see below) reveals three problem areas. First, threshold values for the boundaries between impact classes are not defined. Without such values, assigning industries to one or another group is a somewhat arbitrary process. Second, the class definitions are not universally meaningful. Defining whether a noise is high, low or medium depends to a large extent on *cultural perceptions*. Levels of tolerance to noise, odours and traffic vary widely between cultural groups. For example, a lively next-door party would be considered by the Swiss as an intolerable disturbance, whereas for Cubans it would go largely unnoticed as a part of normal life. Third, the potential impact of industrial activity depends on the *type of technology* it uses. For example, manufacturing a certain product using highly mechanised technology and heavy machinery may be a lot noisier than production of the same item using hand labour or artisanal techniques.

The problem of a universal classification scheme is illustrated by the case of cement-block production in the barrios. This activity is excluded from residential areas by Quito's Master Plan because it is a medium-impact industry, that is, because it nominally produces noise, vibrations, bad odours or excessive movement. However, cement-block production in the barrio employs traditional methods, which are labour intensive, low technology and low production. Levels of noise are in fact very low. With the exception of small electrically driven tumblers that mix sand and water, the entire process of blockmaking is carried out by hand. Blocks are dried in the sun. Cement is delivered by a truck once a week and the produced bricks are distributed by a truck twice a week. Cement piles are small, covered, and therefore generate little dust. No toxic emissions are produced by brick-making. Clearly, traditional cement-block manufacture

¹ Industrial activities are classified into low-impact, medium-impact, high-impact and dangerous types (Municipio de Quito, 1992:87, cuadro 01). Low-impact and medium-impact industries are defined as those which "do not cause disturbances generated by noise, bad odours or excessive movement of people and vehicles". Low-impact industry includes "workshops and non-contaminant small-scale industry with a maximum of 20 workers". This is considered to be compatible with residential areas. Medium-impact industry is "only to be allowed in industrial areas". High-impact industry "may produce noise, vibration and odours and is, therefore, not acceptable in residential areas" (Municipio de Quito, 1992:87).

² Commercial activities are divided into five types: *neighbourhood commerce*, *sector commerce*, *zone commerce*, *special commerce* and *restricted commerce*. *Neighbourhood commerce* (e.g. bakeries, pharmacies) is equivalent to local/neighbourhood commerce and is 'compatible' with residential areas. *Sectorial commerce* (e.g. sale of household-appliances, car check-up services) is equivalent to commercial activity taking place at 'sector' level. *Zone commerce* includes shopping centres and wholesale markets, and *restricted commerce* includes brothels (Municipio de Quito, 1992:85).

does not impact the environment enough to warrant its classification as incompatible with residential land use, particularly in the barrios. It seems that the Municipality's classification addresses only modern, large-scale, mechanised manufacturing operations, such as found in other parts of the city.

The compatibility of commercial and industrial activity in Mena del Hierro. Mena del Hierro is defined by the Master Plan of Quito as an area of residential use ("type A 203", RUQ 1992, Plano 03 & page 90). Accordingly, housing must be the principal land use in the barrio, but neighbourhood commerce and sectorial commerce are also acceptable. By the year 2000, all the commercial activities in the barrio belonged to neighbourhood commerce and sectorial commerce (groceries, bazars, bakeries, liquor stores, pharmacies, tailors, hair-dressers, billiard rooms, restaurants, shoe shops, gas stores, car service centres, electrical repairs and shoe repairs). Thus, all informal commerces in Mena del Hierro are compatible with the Master Plan and hence they can be legalised if the owners so desire.

Concerning the case of informal industries, the majority (60%) of the barrio's industries conform with the regulations. They are classified as low-impact (see table 1) and are therefore compatible with residential use. However, the remaining 40% of industries (most of them owned by local residents) are of medium- and high impact, and therefore are illegal. These include car-repair workshops, cement-block industries and bodywork fitting, all of which are considered to disturb the inhabitants of residential areas. The owners of these industries will never be able to obtain an official permit from the municipal authorities.

Table 1. Compatibility of industries in Mena del Hierro with residential use, according to the Master Plan of Quito.

Low impact "Compatible"	Medium impact "Prohibited"	High impact "Prohibited"
Shoe-maker (1)	Car-repair workshops (2)	Bodywork fitting (1)
Grocery warehouse (2)	Cement-block making (3)	
Plush-toy manufacture (2)		
Cabinet-making (1)		
Jewelery workshop (1)		
Wood-toy workshop (1)		

2.2 Housing density

Quito's Master Plan classifies residential areas into low-, medium- and high density³. Perhaps inspired by the green and quiet north american suburbs, most residential areas on the periphery of the city are designated by the Plan as low-density. In the majority of cases, however, these areas are actually occupied by informal settlements of variable density (such as Mena del Hierro). According to the Plan, all lots in low density areas must be larger than 200 m², they are permitted to host only one construction per lot, and 3 m space must be left between neighbouring houses. In the north-west barrios of Quito, some lots do

³ Low-density areas with at most 250 residents per ha., medium-density areas with at most 400 inhabitants per ha., high-density areas with at most 500 inhabitants per ha. (Municipio de Quito, 1992, Plano 02).

indeed comply with these regulations, but they are a minority. The remainder contravene one or more of the regulations.

Is it really necessary to restrict density as done in the Master Plan? The usual reasons for limiting housing density on city peripheries are to highlight the quality of the landscape and to ensure privacy. These reasons, though valuable, are certainly not the priorities of the urban poor. Their needs and aspirations are to provide housing for themselves and for their kin-groups. Why is higher density on the periphery unacceptable? Evidently, standard arguments, such as the risk of fire, pestilence and groundwater pollution, are not compelling, as high density is permitted in many other areas of the city. To be sure, there is a risk of volcanic eruption and related mud-flows in the north-west of Quito, but the risk is not higher than in the adjacent high-density zones. A reduction of the limit on minimum lot size to 100 m², for example, and a relaxation of the requirement for intervening spaces between houses, would significantly support the survival strategies of the barrio populations. Moreover, smaller and denser lots would enable the total areas available in each barrio to be better planned, without necessarily promoting an increase in population. Free space could thus be obtained for valuable uses such as public spaces and vegetable gardens. Density regulations for peripheral barrios in Quito need to be rethought.

3. Disadvantages of informality and possible solutions

3.1 Lack of access to formal credit

One of the disadvantages of illegality, as outlined above, is that access to formal sources of credit is precluded. How important is this for the urban poor? The experience of Mena del Hierro (see box below) shows that barrio populations have alternative sources of financial support. Kin networks are certainly the most successful of these. The networks link the financial resources of family members that reside in the barrio, in the rural hinterland of the Quito and, with a strongly increasing trend, in other countries. Often financially successful relatives in the barrio or in Europe or North America provide the initial capital for young couples to build a house or start a business, the necessary land and labour being readily available in the barrio through the kin network. Profits from farming in the hinterland that are also invested in the barrio. Families in the countryside often contribute to financing the houses and businesses of their adult children who have migrated to the barrios.

While the kin networks are the main source of financial support for the urban poor, are they sufficient? The answer is no, and the reason is their long-term vulnerability. Support from kinspeople may wane due to illness in the families or to a downturn in overall income. For example, the recent economic crisis in Ecuador has seriously affected owners of informal businesses and this has reduced their ability to help others. The economic equilibrium of the network-based financing system is thus easily threatened.

When social networks fail, credit is usually obtained from informal money-lenders. This solution has always been available to the urban poor, but it is undoubtedly gaining in importance. The money-lenders are free-operating

individuals who are able to provide needed credit in a relatively uncomplicated way, without bureaucratic procedures. However, their rates are exorbitant compared to formal credit rates, and they often use rough methods to force repayment of debts. Obviously, lending policies for owners of buildings or small-scale businesses in informal settlements need to be revised. Informal social networks need to be identified and strengthened by means of economic and training support.

The financial role of informal networks in Mena del Hierro. Most of the residents belong to complex networks of kin, friends, and paisanos. The networks stretch from the immediate neighbourhood out into the rural provinces from which the residents originally migrated. This system of informal networks has been crucial to the establishment of most of the economic activities in the barrio: e.g. groceries, bakeries, transport firms, and car-repair workshops. The support provided by kin, neighbour and *paisano* networks is not restricted to credit but also encompasses flexible and low-cost labour, reciprocal exchange of goods and services, useful contacts, and cheap goods from the countryside. Some of the networks have a less informal character, such as the *Caja de Crédito S-30*. This credit agency is the self-help initiative of a barrio youth group, established to save money and to provide the group's members with capital to start businesses. The *Caja de Crédito* has been relatively successful, clearly due to the fact that a solid social network existed between the members beforehand, fostering trust and the capacity to make decisions easily.

3.2 Lack of public space

Residents of informal settlements tolerate the burden of living without sufficient urban infrastructure for several years. Normally, however, with the help of the government, of non-governmental organizations, and of community self-help groups, barrio residents manage to acquire basic infrastructure and services (water supply, roads, sewerage, electricity). But a need which residents seldom manage to satisfy is that of sufficient public areas for meetings and recreation, especially outdoor sports. Rarely is provision made for public outdoor space when land is informally urbanised. Residents temporarily solve the problem by informally appropriating vacant lots. This is invariably privately-owned land and appropriation is therefore neither a legally satisfactory nor a permanent solution. As land use in the barrios progressively intensifies, essentially all lots become used for other purposes, and so the informal playing fields and meeting places disappear. In mature barrios, by the time that residents' associations are able to turn their collective resources to acquiring recreational facilities, rather than basic infrastructure, all the suitable land is already built up and intensively used. The trend observed in such barrios is that individuals construct playing fields and refreshment stands on their own land and charge entry fees for their use. This mechanism naturally changes the character of the recreational space from truly public, because the land-owners can and do control exactly who has access to their facilities. The lack of permanent public spaces is one of the clearly negative aspects of informal urbanisation.

How can the problem of public spaces be solved? Recognising that the problem boils down to permanent access to land, the joint efforts of community

members, non-governmental organisations, government agencies and the private sector are needed to acquire, develop and administer area for public use. A possible solution is for the state to offer tax incentives to private companies that would buy and develop sports fields and playgrounds in the barrios. The administration of these public spaces should be the responsibility of the community, with the condition that community administrators guarantee access to all community members, independently of their class, geographical origin, age or gender.

Public space in barrio Mena del Hierro. As a consequence of the illegal origin of the barrio, no land was set aside at the outset for outdoor recreation. No provision for public space was made when the *hacienda* was subdivided into *huerto familiares*, because the nominal purpose of these lots was strictly agricultural. Similarly, during the progressive subdivision of the *huertos* by the new owners in the years that followed, no coordinated effort was made to reserve public areas for recreation or other purposes. The only space that has been acquired by the collective resources of the barrio is a small triangle of land that could not be included in the original *huerto familiares* because of size constraints. A community centre and a basketball court have been installed on this land by the barrio committee, and although these facilities are intensively used, the area is by far insufficient. Public space has always been in high demand by the residents because it has such an important role in their socializing patterns. Daily life in Mena del Hierro, as in most barrios, is not individualistic. Rather, it is characterized by a remarkable degree of collectivism. Each resident, whether child, youth or adult, is part of at least one social network in the barrio, and sports fields are the centre of social activity. During the 1990's, more than thirty volleyball, basketball and soccer groups played regularly in the barrio. In the absence of official reserves, the strategies of residents to create public space for sports have included: (a) appropriation of unused land which has an unclear status of ownership; (b) appropriation of private land, sometimes with the tacit or explicit authorization of the land-owner; (c) individual land-owners have adapted their own land into sports fields and made them accessible to local residents in return for cash fees; and (d) use of streets that carry little traffic to play soccer or volleyball.

3.3 Long-term loss of food-producing areas

Urban farming has being praised by many for its positive social and ecological role: it reduces food costs, contributes to secure household nutritional needs, generates employment and helps to maintain soil hydrology, biological diversity and air quality. It has been estimated that in Latin American cities, a family that invests between one and a half days in urban farming is able to save 10-30% of their food expenditure, which represents a significant percentage of their total outlays. In African, Asian and Latin American cities, 10-80% of families are estimated to practise urban farming. In Peruvian and Bolivian cities, for example, approximately half of all households are involved in urban farming. Throughout the South, women are the driving force: two thirds of urban farmers are female (Egziaber et al, 1999).

Although popular elsewhere, urban farming is slowly disappearing from the barrios of Quito. As settlements develop, the areas originally used for crops are often sacrificed for buildings that can be rented for housing, commercial and

manufacturing purposes. The explanation for this phenomenon is that rental income is a better supplement to household budgets. Most workers in the informal sector have no job stability or security and no insurance. This makes them economically vulnerable in the case of illness, accident or a slump in the economy. In this context of uncertainty, cash from rents provides the crucial backup to maintain survival. From the point of view of the poor, the economic advantages of using the land for rentable buildings outweighs the advantages of using the land for food-production. A lot more time and effort needs to be invested in food-producing activities to make them profitable and thus competitive with rental income. Also, food production is generally oriented to self-consumption and not to earning cash. Indeed the expertise for marketing cash crops is generally lacking among residents of informal settlements, and crops lack diversification, being dominated by corn. It is therefore not a surprise that land originally employed for food production acquires other uses over the years.

Despite these trends and deficiencies, efforts should be made to preserve and foster urban farming, owing to its potentially important role in poverty alleviation and environmental protection. Urban farming should be highly viable in the barrios of Quito, as many of the lots are still large (25% of the barrios were originally subdivided for *huertos familiares* -vegetable gardens- with lot sizes of 2500 m²), climate is adequate and good-quality water is available. The potential for urban farming is currently not fully exploited by residents of the barrios, and in comparison to other cities of the South (e.g. Peruvian cities or cities in Asia), support from official, academic and private sectors is limited. Several measures could be taken to improve urban farming: (a) the variety of products which are planted in the barrios could be expanded to better cover nutritional needs; (b) the possibilities of marketing agricultural produce from the barrios could be explored in order to create employment, particularly for women; (c) farming practices could be modified to be more beneficial to the environment. For example, the concentration of barrios at the foothills of the Pichincha Mountain in Quito has led to deforestation and consequent destabilisation of slopes and water catchments by erosion. This in turn has caused frequent landslides with human and material losses. Combining urban farming with agroforestry could be a promising field to alleviate these problems.

How should urban farming be best supported? External assistance is indispensable to protect and promote urban farming in the barrios. Barrio residents cannot do this alone. Experience shows that urban farming thrives in countries where explicit support is provided by official authorities. Several aspects of the problem need to be addressed simultaneously. First, it has to be ensured, via credits or subsidies from private and public sectors, that urban farming remains competitive with the alternative of rental income. Second, urban farming needs organisational support, to help individual farmers pool their resources and market their products together. Finally, technical support on crop diversification, production and marketing is also required.

4. Conclusions: addressing land use in the barrios from an integrated perspective

Informal land use has been analysed here from an integrated perspective including legal, social and cultural aspects. Thus informality is recognised to consist of three elements: illegality of land use, simultaneous use of land for living and for producing, and spatial concentration of kin-related households. Using this definition, informal land use in the barrios of Quito has been evaluated with respect to the modernisation, neoliberal and grassroots views of the phenomenon.

Modernisation considers informal land use to be a problem because it deviates from the segregationist planning model. However, the empirical findings presented here demonstrate that the mixture of residential and production functions in the barrios is a viable -and for the present at least- the only solution for the socio-economic plight of the urban poor. Informal land use should therefore be viewed as a solution, not as a problem. The modernist model is seriously flawed, because it is based on values that are not appropriate to the socio-economic reality of the majority of the populations in the cities of the South. The grassroots perspective emphasizes the beneficial effects of informal land use in alleviating poverty. The empirical case studies analysed in this paper support this view. Informal land use is seen to be a valid means for the urban poor to solve problems of shelter, food production, income generation and social integration.

Neoliberals argue that the main disadvantage of illegality is the absence of land titles that would enable the urban poor to borrow from formal sources and hence develop. It follows that property laws should be revised to facilitate legalisation. There are several flaws in this argumentation. First, illegality in most barrios of Quito is not characterised by a lack of land titles. The barrio residents usually have titles to the land they occupy but instead they lack the necessary building or business permits to apply for formal credit. The issue in this case is thus not one of not complying with property laws but with *land-use regulations*. Second, arguing that the poor are dependent on formal borrowing for their development is not true. *Informal networks* are a successful -albeit vulnerable- alternative for the poor to finance their houses and businesses. Third, the neoliberal analysis of the disadvantages of informality has focused exclusively on economic aspects. Social and cultural disadvantages, such as the lack of sufficient and adequate *public spaces* in the barrios and the long-term loss of *food-producing areas*, are important and warrant attention.

In order to assess whether current land-use regulations are appropriate for the barrios of Quito, the Urban Master Plan of the city has been examined. In comparison with modernist models, the Plan provides a relatively flexible legal framework, but there are still two areas which constitute unnecessary barriers to land use in the barrios. The first concerns the definition of environmental impact standards based on modern, large-scale operations in industrial centres, and on the tolerances of North America and Western Europe. The industries in the barrios may manufacture the same products as the large-scale counterparts, but the methods employed are largely artisanal. Their environmental impact is

therefore quite different, and the perceptions of these impacts by residents are also different. Environmental impact standards are clearly not universal but need to be adapted to local circumstances. Second, forcing barrio areas to be low-density is a completely unnecessary restriction. There are no compelling arguments against high density per se. Density regulations for the barrios need to be rethought. As argued with empirical evidence in this paper, a relaxation of density regulations could liberate valuable space for public uses and at the same time support the survival strategies of barrio populations.

The implications of the above conclusions are that land-use policies for the barrios need to go beyond the economic and legal views. Social, cultural and ecological aspects need to be incorporated. This means that, besides reassessing land use policies for informal settlements, it is important to devise measures which support informal networks, generate public space and foster urban farming. Policy definition and implementation will only be successful when technical and financial partnerships are formed between the community, non-governmental organisations, government agencies, private enterprise and international development agencies.

It is evident that more case studies of informal settlements are required to better understand the following issues: (a) the adequacy of land-use regulations in Urban Master Plans; (b) the technology used by informal barrio industries needs better documentation to help formulate appropriate environmental impact standards. Similarly, the tolerance of residents to environmental impacts needs to be studied in more detail; (c) the strengths and weaknesses of informal networks in supporting housing and small-scale business; (d) the need for public space must be better quantified and measures to redress inadequacies need to be developed; (e) the performance, popularity and problems of urban farming in the barrios need to be monitored and the reasons behind the trends need to be elucidated.

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